

Urban Policy Interventions to Reduce Traffic-Related Emissions and Air Pollution: A Systematic Evidence Map

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1 **ABBREVIATIONS**

2 **BC**.....Black carbon

3 **BS**.....Black smoke

4 **CAC**.....Catalytic converter

5 **CARTEEH**.....Center for Advancing Research in Transportation Emissions, Energy and Health

6 **CO**.....Carbon monoxide

7 **DALY**.....Disability-adjusted life year

8 **DOC**.....Diesel oxidation catalyst

9 **DPF**.....Diesel particulate filter

10 **EC**.....Elemental carbon

11 **EGR**.....Exhaust gas recirculation

12 **EV**.....Electric vehicle

13 **GHG**.....Greenhouse gas

14 **HC**..... Hydrocarbon

15 **HEV**.....Hybrid electric vehicle

16 **KonSULT**.....Knowledgebase on Sustainable Urban Land use and Transport

17 **LEZ**.....Low emission zone

18 **MFR**..... Maximum Feasible Reductions

19 **NAAQS**.....National Ambient Air Quality Standards

20 **MPO**.....Metropolitan Planning Organization

21 **NH₃**.....Ammonia

22 **NO**.....Nitric oxide

23 **NO₂**.....Nitrogen dioxide

24 **NO_x**.....Nitrogen oxides

25 **OC**.....Organic carbon

26 **OECD**..... Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development

27 **PICO**.....Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome

28 **PM**.....Particulate matter

29 **PM₁**.....Particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 1 micrometer

30 **PM_{2.5}**.....Particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 2.5 micrometers

31 **PM₁₀**Particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 10 micrometers

32 **PM_{absorbance}**.....Blackness of PM filters as a representation of BC or EC

33 **PM_{coarse}**.....Difference between PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}

34 **PM_x**.....Particulate matter with diameters of mixed sizes

35 **PPM**.....Parts per million

36 **PRISMA**.....Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analysis

37 **ROG**.....Reactive organic gasses

38 **RSPM**.....Respirable suspended particulate matter

39 **SEM**.....Systematic evidence map

40 **SO₂**.....Sulfur dioxide

41 **SO_x**.....Sulfur oxides

42 **SOA**.....Secondary organic aerosols

43 **SPM**.....Suspended particulate matter

44 **TC**.....Total carbon

45 **TOG**.....Total organic gasses

46 **TRAP**.....Traffic-related air pollution

47 **TRID**.....Transportation Research International Documentation

48 **UFP**.....Ultrafine particle

49 **VOC**.....Volatile organic compound

50 **WHO**..... World Health Organization

51 **Abstract**

52 **Background** Urban areas are hot spots for human exposure to air pollution, which originates in
53 big part from traffic. As the urban population continues to grow, a greater number of people risk
54 exposure to traffic-related air pollution (TRAP) and its adverse, costly health effects. In many
55 cities, there is a need and scope for improvement in air quality through targeted policy
56 interventions, which continue to grow and include rapidly changing technologies.

57 **Objective** This systematic evidence map (SEM) examines and characterizes peer-reviewed
58 evidence on urban-level policy interventions aimed at reducing traffic emissions and/or TRAP
59 from on-road mobile sources, thus potentially reducing human exposures and adverse health
60 effects and producing various co-benefits.

61 **Methods** This SEM's methods follow a previously peer reviewed and published protocol with
62 very minor deviations, explicitly outlined in this paper. Articles indexed in Public Affairs Index,
63 TRID, Medline and Embase were searched, limited to English, published between January 1,
64 2000, and June 1, 2020. Covidence was used to screen articles for inclusion at the title/abstract
65 and full text levels based on previously developed eligibility criteria. Data for included articles
66 was extracted and documented manually into an Excel database. Data visualizations were created
67 in Tableau.

68 **Results** We identified 7528 unique articles from database searches and included 365 unique
69 articles in the final SEM. There were 58 unique policy interventions, and a total of 1,092 unique
70 policy scenarios. The policy interventions fell under 6 overarching policy categories: 1) pricing,
71 2) land use, 3) infrastructure, 4) behavioral, 5) technology, and 6) management, standards, and
72 services, with the latter being the most studied category. For geographic location, 453 policy
73 scenarios were studied in Europe, followed by 320 in Asia, 206 in North America, 57 in South
74 America, 8 in Africa, and 7 in Australia. Alternative fuel technology was the most frequently
75 studied intervention at 265 times, followed by vehicle emission regulation at 126 times. The least
76 frequently studied interventions were vehicle ownership taxes, greenspace or blue space, and
77 studded tire regulations, which were studied once each. A mere 3% of studies address all
78 elements of the full-chain—traffic emissions, TRAP, exposures, and health. The evidence
79 recorded for each intervention is hosted in an open-access, query-able Excel database available
80 on the CARTEEH Data Hub (<https://carteetehdata.org/library/dataset/urban-policy-intervention-f08c>), and a complementary interactive visualization tool
81 (<https://tableau.tamu.edu/t/TTI/views/SEMDataVisualizationV2/SEMVisualizationDashboard?:s>
82 [howAppBanner=false&:display_count=n&:showVizHome=n&:origin=viz_share_link](https://tableau.tamu.edu/t/TTI/views/SEMDataVisualizationV2/SEMVisualizationDashboard?:s)). Using
83 these outputs, we show how users can find more about the effectiveness of the 1,092 included
84 policy scenarios. For example, the full implementation of the most advanced technical measures
85 to reduce emissions in Gdansk and Katowice, Poland, was modeled to reduce NO₂ and PM₁₀
86 canyon street increments from 16-53 µg/m³ to 7-24 µg/m³, and from 5-15 µg/m³ to 0.2-2.4
87 µg/m³, respectively.
88

89 **Conclusion** This is the first peer-reviewed SEM to compile international evidence on urban-level
90 policy interventions to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP in the context of human exposure

91 and health effects, whilst also documenting reported enablers, barriers, and co-benefits. The
92 open-access Excel database and interactive visualization tool can be valuable resources for
93 practitioners, policymakers, and researchers. Future updates to the SEM and its database and
94 visualization tool are recommended.

95 **Protocol Registration** Sanchez, K.A., Foster, M., Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., May, A.D., Ramani,
96 T., Zietsman, J. and Khreis, H., 2020. Urban policy interventions to reduce traffic emissions and
97 traffic-related air pollution: Protocol for a systematic evidence map. Environment international,
98 142, p.105826.

99 ***Keywords: Urban; City; Policy; Intervention; Emissions; Traffic-Related Air Pollution;***
100 ***Exposure; Health; Climate; Co-Benefits***

101

102 **Introduction and Rationale**

103 Road traffic is one of the main contributors to air pollution and greenhouse gasses around the
104 world (Guarnieri and Balmes, 2014; McDuffie et al., 2020; McDuffie et al., 2021) and
105 significantly contributes to particulate matter (PM) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions
106 (European Environment Agency, 2016). In urban areas of the United States, vehicles contribute
107 up to over a third of the ambient particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 2.5
108 micrometers (PM_{2.5}) (Hammond et al., 2008), while globally, 25% of urban PM_{2.5} is contributed
109 by traffic (Karagulian et al., 2015). In Europe, urban traffic contributes up to 56% of ambient
110 nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and approximately 39% of particulate matter with a diameter equal to or
111 less than 10 micrometers (PM₁₀) concentrations (Sundvor et al., 2012). There are broadly two
112 types of traffic emissions: exhaust and non-exhaust. Exhaust emissions result from incomplete
113 fuel combustion, whereas non-exhaust emissions are a result of brake wear, engine wear, tire
114 wear, road surface wear, evaporative emissions, and re-suspended crystal and street dust particles
115 (Frosina et al., 2018; Rubin et al., 2006; Thorpe and Harrison, 2008). For PM, the non-exhaust
116 component is significant. For example, in the Ruhr area of Germany, exhaust, abrasion, and
117 resuspension (non-exhaust) emissions respectively contribute to 22%, 22% and 56% of PM₁₀
118 levels at an urban background location, and 27%, 15%, and 58% at a streetside location
119 (Weinbruch et al., 2014).

120 Traffic emissions disperse into the ambient air as traffic-related air pollution (TRAP), which
121 degrades ambient air quality. Humans exposed to TRAP are at risk of developing a wide range of
122 adverse health effects, including, but not limited to, premature mortality, lung cancer, adverse
123 respiratory effects, cardiovascular effects, cerebrovascular effects, reproductive and pregnancy
124 effects, neurological and cognitive effects, metabolic effects, and bone effects (Khreis, 2020;
125 Health Effects Institute, 2022). In addition to the negative physical and mental health effects
126 associated with TRAP, there is also an immense financial burden which includes the cost of
127 hospitalizations, medical visits, medication, missed school days, loss of earnings from missed
128 workdays, and/or death (Brandt et al., 2014, 2012; Nurmagambetov et al., 2018; Roy et al.,
129 2011). After the Global Burden of Disease Study (2015), the OECD carried out a follow-up
130 study in 2017 that drew on the epidemiological evidence gathered from that study to examine the
131 mortality rates caused by ambient air pollution (AAP) – ambient particulate matter pollution
132 (APMP) – and ambient ozone pollution (AOP) in 41 countries over five-year intervals from 2000
133 to 2015 (Roy and Braathen, 2017). According to the study, in 2015, ambient air pollution
134 (APMP + AOP) cost OECD nations \$1.89 trillion, the BRIICS (Brazil, Russia, India, Indonesia,
135 China, and South Africa) \$3.176 trillion, and these 41 countries together \$5.64 trillion (Roy and
136 Braathen, 2017).

137 Urban areas are hotspots for human exposure to air pollution originating from road traffic (Kura
138 et al., 2013), and these areas are growing rapidly. Approximately two-thirds of the global
139 population is estimated to reside in urban areas by 2050 (United Nations and Department of
140 Economic and Social Affairs Population Division, 2015). Rapid urban growth and an increasing

141 number of urban residents indicate that a greater quantity of people will be at risk of TRAP
142 exposure and its adverse health effects. Unfortunately, many cities around the world struggle to
143 meet air quality standards and guidelines despite growing evidence linking traffic, air pollution,
144 exposure, and adverse health effects (World Health Organization, 2014). The World Health
145 Organization (WHO) estimates that merely one in ten people around the globe lives in a city that
146 meets WHO air quality guidelines for PM_{2.5} (5 µg/m³ annual mean and 15 µg/m³ 24-hour mean)
147 and PM₁₀ (15 µg/m³ annual mean and 45 µg/m³ 24-hour mean) (World Health Organization,
148 2021). In the United States, many areas exceed National Ambient Air Quality Standards
149 (NAAQS) for PM_{2.5} (12 µg/m³ annual mean) and 8-hour ozone (0.070 parts per million) (U.S.
150 Environmental Protection Agency, 2019; United States Environmental Protection Agency,
151 2016). In 2012, over 20 million people lived in areas failing to meet the PM_{2.5} NAAQS (United
152 States Environmental Protection Agency, 2020a), and in 2015, over 122 million people lived in
153 areas failing to meet the 8-hour ozone NAAQS (United States Environmental Protection Agency,
154 2020b). Similarly, in Europe in 2010, 41% and 7% of the urban population lived in areas
155 exceeding European Union air quality standards for PM₁₀ 24-hour limit value (50 µg/m³) and
156 NO₂ annual limit value (40 µg/m³), respectively (European Commission, 2019; Sundvor et al.,
157 2012).

158 Importantly, the adverse health effects associated with TRAP, and air pollution in general, are
159 observed at relatively low concentrations well below standards and guideline values (Beelen et
160 al., 2014; Belanger et al., 2006; Castro et al., 2009; Chen and Omaye, 2001; Loxham et al., 2019;
161 MacIntyre et al., 2014; Nishimura et al., 2013; Pedersen et al., 2013; Scoggins et al., 2004; Wei
162 et al., 2019; World Health Organization, 2013). Currently, there is no known “safe” limit for air
163 pollution levels where exposure to air pollution does not result in adverse health effects
164 (Hitchcock et al., 2014; Khreis, 2020). Notably, ambient pollutant levels from pollutants like
165 ammonia, black carbon (BC), and ultrafine particles (UFP) are unregulated and are not routinely
166 measured or studied even though they are abundant at the local scale due to traffic activity and
167 elicit adverse health effects (Cape et al., 2004; Dennenkamp et al., 2002; Durbin et al., 2001;
168 Khreis et al., 2017a; Luben et al., 2017; Onat and Stakeeva, 2013; Perrino et al., 2003, 2002;
169 Skjøth and Hertel, 2013; Tomlin et al., 2010). Although technologies, such as electric vehicles
170 including hybrid electric vehicles (HEV) and battery electric vehicles (BEV), will aid in reducing
171 traffic emissions and TRAP, there are still challenges regarding their adoption and
172 implementation (Hannan et al., 2014), and concerns that their effect on non-exhaust emissions
173 may be overall negative (Timmers and Achten, 2016).

174 Reducing traffic emissions and TRAP remains an important issue to address in the existing and
175 rapidly evolving urban context. It is important to document policy interventions (also referred to
176 as “measures”, “strategies”, or “practices”) that may be implemented in urban areas to reduce
177 traffic emissions and TRAP, across a wide range of pollutants, thus providing the evidence base
178 for limiting exposures and adverse health effects for urban populations. There is currently limited
179 evidence available on the effectiveness of urban policy interventions to reduce traffic emissions
180 and/or TRAP. This Systematic Evidence Map (SEM) fills this gap by identifying, describing, and
181 summarizing the global evidence base on policy interventions that may be implemented in urban
182 areas to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP. The benefit of conducting this SEM

183 encompassing multiple urban-level policy interventions from around the globe is that it will
184 provide a broad and a high-level overview of the evidence base without restriction on the
185 intervention type, pollutant, or location. Considering studies without geographic restriction
186 provides an opportunity to learn from different countries and become aware of more progressive
187 or atypical policies that may not be implemented in certain areas of the world, in addition to
188 better understanding their potential impacts and initiating discussions about their transferability.
189 Furthermore, understanding the latest information on urban policy interventions is of increasing
190 value especially as new types of policy interventions and technologies continue to emerge and as
191 evidence continues to emerge on the negative consequences of pollution. Proactively collecting
192 and understanding information on emerging policy interventions and technologies may also lead
193 to the early identification and potentially the mitigation of unintended consequences.

194 Although there are previous reviews (Bigazzi and Rouleau, 2017; Bradley et al., 2019; Burns et
195 al., 2019; Conlan et al., 2016; Henschel et al., 2012; Holman et al., 2015; Slovic et al., 2016;
196 Wagner and Rutherford, 2013), each has limitations in scope and/or methodology. Key
197 differences from the current SEM are listed in Table A.1 and discussed in more detail in a
198 previously published protocol (Sanchez et al., 2020). Of the note-worthy differences are that only
199 one review reported methods used prior to publication (Burns et al., 2014), and none of the
200 previous reviews hosted results in an open-access database or tool. Indeed, to the best of our
201 knowledge, this SEM is the first to identify and compile international evidence for urban policy
202 interventions together in the context of human exposure and health, in an open-access and query-
203 able Excel database and interactive visualization tool. Therefore, the outputs we provide contain
204 valuable information for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers, and future updates are
205 encouraged by other researchers, following methods explicitly detailed in Sanchez et al. (2020)
206 and this paper.

Review	Hosts results in an open-access, query-able database	Reports methods used prior to publication	Focuses on traffic emissions and TRAP as primary outcomes	Considers a comprehensive set of interventions to mitigate traffic emissions and/or TRAP	Considers a comprehensive set of traffic-related air pollutants	Considers a comprehensive set of on-road vehicles	Focuses on traffic emissions and TRAP in the context of human exposure and health	Exclusive to the urban level	Considers international evidence
Bigazzi and Rouleau 2017			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
Bradley et al. 2019				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Burns et al. 2019		✓		✓		✓	✓		✓
Conlan et al. 2016			✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
Henschel et al. 2012					✓	✓	✓		✓
Holman et al. 2015			✓			✓	✓	✓	
Slovic et al. 2016			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Wagner and Rutherford 2013			✓	✓	✓				✓
Current SEM	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table A.1 Differences Between Previous Reviews and the Current SEM

209 **Methods**

210 We previously published a protocol to detail the objective, scope, and methods used to conduct
211 this SEM (Sanchez et al., 2020). This SEM adheres to the preferred reporting items for
212 systematic review and meta-analysis statement (PRISMA) (Moher et al., 2009) with
213 modifications considered for a SEM. The SEM will be uploaded to Zenodo (an open access
214 research repository) before the peer-review process, and an updated version will be uploaded
215 after the peer-review process to promote transparency of changes made. The final accepted SEM
216 version will be uploaded and accessible in Zenodo along with all previous versions (DOI:
217 10.5281/zenodo.6937363).

218 *Objective*

219 The objective of this SEM is to examine and characterize the evidence on urban-level policy
220 interventions that can be implemented by urban authorities to reduce traffic emissions and/or
221 TRAP from on-road mobile sources, thus potentially reducing human exposures and adverse
222 health impacts and producing various social, environmental, climate and economic co-benefits.
223 We also created an open-access, interactive database in the form of a Microsoft Excel sheet to
224 facilitate the identification of relevant trends and gaps in the evidence base and serve as the
225 foundation for future research, practice, and policy recommendations. The Excel database has
226 been uploaded to the [CARTEEH Data Hub](https://carteehdata.org/library/dataset/urban-policy-intervention-f08c) (Center for Advancing Research in Transportation
227 Emissions Energy and Health, 2020) and can be accessed at
228 (<https://carteehdata.org/library/dataset/urban-policy-intervention-f08c>). Additionally, the Excel
229 database is included in the Supplementary Material.

230 *Scope of the SEM*

231 Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome (PICO) items are outlined to clearly describe the
232 scope of this SEM (Table A.2).

<i>Population</i>	The population of interest is the urban population. We included populations residing in urban clusters and urbanized areas. Urban clusters are densely settled territories that contain between 2,500 and 50,000 people, and urbanized areas are densely settled territories that contain at least 50,000 people, as defined by the United States Census Bureau (U.S. Department of Commerce, 2012).
<i>Intervention</i>	The intervention refers to urban-level policy interventions to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP that can be implemented by urban authorities. For the purpose of this paper, “policy intervention” refers to the set of possible strategies, measures, or practices undertaken to achieve a policy objective. In this case, the objective is to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP concentrations originating from on-road mobile sources in urban areas. We consider policy interventions that reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP

	concentrations directly (i.e., the specific aim of the intervention is to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP) or indirectly (i.e., the specific aim of the intervention is not to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP but is still observed – for example, some policies may aim to reduce congestion or improve road safety). “Urban authorities” refer to cities, air agencies, local authorities, including county and district councils, and metropolitan planning organizations (MPOs) or districts.
<i>Comparator</i>	The comparator is the baseline or absence of the urban-level policy intervention of interest.
<i>Outcome</i>	The primary outcomes are traffic emissions and TRAP concentrations. Secondary outcomes are human exposures and health effects or impacts, and secondary items of interest are enablers and barriers to intervention implementation and co-benefits. Secondary outcomes and items of interest will only be reported as available for studies reporting a primary outcome.

233 Table A.2 PICO Items

234 *Eligibility Criteria*

235 The eligibility criteria used to determine whether potential articles were included or excluded in
 236 this SEM are described below. We included articles that met all the following criteria:

- 237 ● Articles that investigate policy interventions implemented in urbanized areas (densely
 238 settled territory that contains 50,000 or more people) or urban clusters (densely settled
 239 territory that contains at least 2,500 people but fewer than 50,000 people) as defined by
 240 the United States Census Bureau (U.S. Department of Commerce, 2012)
- 241 ● Articles that investigate urban-level policy interventions’ impact on traffic emissions
 242 (exhaust or non-exhaust) and/or TRAP originating from mobile on-road traffic: BC,
 243 elemental carbon (EC), hydrocarbons (HCs), carbon monoxide (CO), nitric oxide (NO),
 244 NO₂, NO_x, sulfur dioxide (SO₂), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, difference between PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}
 245 (PM_{coarse}), blackness of PM filters as a representation of BC or EC (PM_{absorbance}),
 246 particulate matter with diameters of mixed sizes (PM_x), UFP, and volatile organic
 247 compounds (VOCs) or other traffic-related air pollutants/pollution
- 248 ● Articles that investigate past, current, future (hypothetical) or hypothetical changes in
 249 traffic emissions and/or TRAP
- 250 ● Articles reported in the English language
- 251 ● Articles published between January 1, 2000, and June 1, 2020
- 252 ● Articles that are peer-reviewed

253 We excluded articles that met any of the following criteria:

- 254 ● Articles that exclusively investigate policy interventions implemented at the
- 255 state/regional or federal/national level or in non-urban areas (e.g., rural areas)
- 256 ● Articles that exclusively investigate urban-level policy intervention impact on an
- 257 outcome other than the primary outcomes, traffic emissions and TRAP (e.g., traffic
- 258 congestion, traffic noise, traffic safety, etc.)
- 259 ● Articles that exclusively investigate off-road traffic emissions (e.g., boats, planes, trains,
- 260 construction equipment, etc.)
- 261 ● Articles that exclusively investigate non-traffic related emissions or non-traffic related air
- 262 pollution (e.g., wildfires, wood smoke, industrial and indoor combustion emissions, etc.)
- 263 ● Articles that exclusively investigate human exposures and/or health outcomes because of
- 264 an urban-level policy intervention (which for our purpose are treated as secondary
- 265 outcomes)
- 266 ● Articles that exclusively investigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (which for our
- 267 purpose are treated as a co-benefit)
- 268 ● Articles that do not investigate a policy intervention (e.g., source apportionment studies)
- 269 ● Articles that investigate a policy proxy (e.g., strikes, lockdowns, etc.) or do not
- 270 investigate a policy intervention (e.g., source apportionment studies)
- 271 ● Articles that are not original studies or do not provide original data (e.g., reviews)
- 272 ● Articles that are conference or symposium proceedings, books, book chapters, or reports
- 273

274 *Literature Search*

275 We searched the [Public Affairs Index](#) (EBSCO, n.d.), [Transportation Research International](#)

276 [Documentation](#) (TRID) (Transportation Research Board, n.d.), Medline (Ebsco), and Embase

277 (Ovid) for relevant articles published in the English language between January 1, 2000, and June

278 1, 2020. The exact searches used to identify relevant articles in the databases are provided in the

279 Supplementary Material (Table S.1). In line with our published protocol, gray literature was

280 excluded from the literature search. Due to time and resource limitations, and the large number

281 of papers returned from our electronic searches, it was not possible to consider articles from

282 reference lists, other projects and expert knowledge, and the CARTEEH Literature Library

283 (<https://www.carteeh.org/carteeh-literature-library/>), which is a deviation from our published

284 protocol (Sanchez et al., 2020). These resources can be included in future iterations of the

285 resulting database.

286 *Study Screening*

287 Results from the literature search were imported into [Covidence](#) (Veritas Health Innovation, n.d.)

288 which was utilized to store and screen potential studies for inclusion or exclusion. Covidence

289 automatically identified and removed duplicate records. Then, the screening process was

290 conducted at two levels: 1) title and abstract screening and 2) full-text screening.

291 KS and HK reviewed the screening process and the data extraction and coding process at the

292 outset and selected papers were reviewed together to ensure all processes were well-defined,

293 similarly understood and agreed upon. Uncertainties were resolved through discussion until
294 consensus was achieved. A third opinion was sought from another reviewer for any
295 disagreements. Titles and abstracts of all identified articles were screened by KS, and a random
296 20% was independently screened by JB. Any disagreements were resolved by HK. All articles
297 potentially meeting our inclusion criteria were retrieved, and their full papers were reviewed by
298 KS with a random 20% independently reviewed by HK. Any disagreements were resolved by JB.
299 Any studies that were not screened in duplicate which were unclear were discussed with HK and
300 any disagreement was resolved by JB. A reason for exclusion was provided for each of the
301 articles that were excluded after the full-text screening, as shown in the Supplementary Material
302 (Table S.2). Additionally, we indicated which articles were among the 20% screened in duplicate
303 at the title and abstract level and full-text level, and we provided the agreement rate across those
304 articles in the Supplementary Material (Tables S.3 and S.4).

305 *Data Extraction, Coding, and Storage*

306 Data were extracted and documented manually in Microsoft Excel by KS according to the
307 predefined categories and codes outlined in the Supplementary Material (Table S.5). Three
308 authors, HK, TR, and JB reviewed 20% of the coded data for consistency. Any discrepancies
309 were noted during the review of coded data and shared with KS to achieve a resolution. If one
310 study included several interventions, each intervention was considered separately. More detail on
311 data collection and coding, including the level at which data was collected for each category, is
312 specified in the Supplementary Material (Table S.5). If there was missing data from a study, KS
313 requested information from the corresponding author via email. If no response was received, KS
314 followed up twice via email at one and three weeks. If there was still no response, the missing
315 data was labeled “N/A” for “Not Available”. Studies with missing data are documented in the
316 Supplementary Material (Table S.6).

317 *Interactive Data Visualization*

318 Interactive data visualization was created by RJ using Tableau Server Version: 2021.1.10. The
319 dashboard helps the user to visualize the locations of policy interventions and filter and visualize
320 the effect of different policy interventions and other characteristics such as health effects or
321 impacts, policy enablers, policy barriers, co-benefits, country of study, analysis start and end
322 years, publication year and scientific journals. The dashboard is hosted on Texas A&M
323 Transportation Institute’s tableau server and can be accessed at
324 [https://tableau.tamu.edu/t/TTI/views/SEMDataVisualizationV2/SEMVisualizationDashboard?sh](https://tableau.tamu.edu/t/TTI/views/SEMDataVisualizationV2/SEMVisualizationDashboard?showAppBanner=false&:display_count=n&:showVizHome=n&:origin=viz_share_link)
325 [owAppBanner=false&:display_count=n&:showVizHome=n&:origin=viz_share_link](https://tableau.tamu.edu/t/TTI/views/SEMDataVisualizationV2/SEMVisualizationDashboard?showAppBanner=false&:display_count=n&:showVizHome=n&:origin=viz_share_link).

326 **Results**

327 *Search Results*

328 Figure A.1 is a study flow diagram outlining the number of articles that were retrieved from our
329 database searches and the number of articles evaluated at each screening level. 7528 unique
330 articles were identified after 1602 duplicates were removed. 6930 articles were excluded after the

331 title and abstract screening, leaving 598 to be screened at the full-text level. 233 articles were
 332 excluded after the full-text screening. Exclusion reasons for all articles excluded at the full-text
 333 level are provided in the Supplementary Material (Table S.2). Notably, ten duplicates remained
 334 that were identified at the full-text screening level and were labeled as such for the exclusion
 335 reason. Finally, 365 studies were included in this SEM.

336 Of the random 20% of titles and abstracts independently screened by JB (1500 records shown in
 337 Table S.3), the agreement rate between KS and JB was 92.8%. Disagreements were resolved by
 338 HK. Of the random 20% of full papers independently screened by HK (120 records shown in
 339 Table S.4), the agreement rate between KS and HK was 88.5%. Disagreements were resolved by
 340 JB. In addition, KS and HK met to discuss in detail the disagreements and the resolutions and
 341 ensure that consensus on how to screen in similar future instances was achieved. Other studies
 342 that were not screened in duplicate which were unclear were discussed with HK and any
 343 disagreement was resolved by JB.

344
 345 Figure A.1 Study Flow Diagram

346 *Summary of Evidence*

347 Data were recorded for a total of 1,092 policy intervention scenarios from 365 articles since
 348 some articles investigated more than one policy scenario. Half of the included articles

349 investigated only 1 policy scenario while the remaining half investigated 2 or more policy
 350 scenarios. As many as 58 individual policy scenarios were investigated within a single article
 351 (Mediavilla-Sahagun and ApSimon, 2003). The 365 included articles were published across 86
 352 scientific journals. Most articles were published in Atmospheric Environment with 49 of the
 353 included articles, followed by Transportation Research Part D with 46 articles, Science of the
 354 Total Environment with 32 articles, and Transportation Research Record with 31 articles. The
 355 remaining 82 journals each published 13 articles or less.

356 Furthermore, included articles were published between the years 2000 and 2020. An increasing
 357 trend in the published evidence, especially within the last ten years, supports that there is a
 358 growing body of literature on this topic and a need to update this SEM in the future if this
 359 evidence base is to be mapped again. Most articles were published in 2019 with 35 published
 360 articles, followed by 34 articles published in 2017, 32 articles published in 2018, and 29 articles
 361 in 2020. Notably, the literature search parameters limited publications up to June 1, 2020, so the
 362 29 articles published in 2020 only reflect half of that year. Most articles included in this SEM
 363 were classified as case study/case series study types at 99.2%. Cross-sectional studies composed
 364 0.5% of study types, and case-control studies composed 0.2% of study types for articles included
 365 in the SEM. The study type was classified based on the predefined categories outlined in the
 366 protocol and the Supplementary Material (Table S.5). There were no Case Report, Cohort,
 367 Ecological, Quasi-Experiments, or Randomized Controlled Trials, which are mostly relevant in
 368 the medical and epidemiological literature, and less so for the assessment of traffic emissions and
 369 TRAP policy interventions.

370 This SEM considered 58 types of unique policies which fell within 1 of 6 overarching policy
 371 categories predefined in our protocol: 1) pricing, 2) land-use, 3) infrastructure, 4) behavioral, 5)
 372 technology, and 6) management, standards, and services as outlined in the Supplementary
 373 Material (Table S.5). The 6 overarching policy categories were adapted from the Policy
 374 Guidebook of the Knowledgebase on Sustainable Urban Land use and Transport (KonSULT)
 375 (University of Leeds, 2016). There were 8 types of pricing policy, 6 types of land-use policy, 11
 376 types of infrastructure policy, 4 types of behavioral policy, 8 types of technology policy, and 21
 377 types of management, standards, and services policy. Management, standards, and services
 378 policies were studied most frequently and are documented in 71.7% of scenarios followed by
 379 technology policies in 36.5% of scenarios, pricing policies in 17.6% of scenarios, infrastructure
 380 policies in 18.0% of scenarios, behavioral policies in 10.6% of scenarios, and land-use policies in
 381 7.1% of scenarios. Table A.3 outlines the frequency of each policy intervention within the 6
 382 overarching policy categories.

Policy Category	Policy Intervention	Frequency Studied
Pricing	Air pollution charging fees	4
	Congestion charging	28
	Fuel taxes or price increase	26
	Mileage-based user fees	4

	Parking charges	55
	Road pricing	51
	Pricing incentives	23
	Vehicle ownership taxes	1
Land-Use	Development density and mixed developments	42
	Parking expansion	2
	Superblock development	2
	Transit-oriented development	18
	Urban sprawl	8
	Urban transport planning	5
Infrastructure	Active transportation infrastructure	26
	Bus rapid transit or mass rapid transit	34
	Greenspace or blue space	1
	Park and ride	9
	Public transportation infrastructure	31
	Roadway development	23
	Solid roadside barrier	8
	Speed bump development	18
	Street ventilation	2
	Unconventional intersection or intersection alteration	22
	Vegetative roadside barrier, surface, or roof	23
Behavioral	Active or non-motorized transport (i.e., bike or walk) promotion or shift	31
	Flexible work arrangements	26
	Public transit promotion or shift	47
	Ride sharing promotion or shift	12
Technology	Alternative fuel technology	265
	Alternative vehicle technology	12
	Electronic toll technology	3
	Material coating	6
	Real-time passenger information	2
	Speed control technology	5
	Stop/Start technology	2
	Vehicle retrofitting	104
Management, Standards, and Services	Fleet management	56
	Fuel regulation or restriction	35
	High occupancy vehicle lane	13
	Inspection and maintenance program	18
	Intelligent transport system	44

Low emission zone	54
Loading, unloading, and/or idling regulation	18
Parking standards, reduction, or regulation	16
Public transportation expansion	47
Public transportation regulation	27
Speed limit regulation or reduction	42
Street cleaning	4
Studded tire regulation	1
Traffic signal optimization	28
Vehicle or manufacturing alteration	4
Vehicle emission regulation	126
Vehicle purchase restriction	7
Vehicle rerouting or route optimization	17
Vehicle retirement or replacement	112
Vehicle shift	2
Vehicle use restriction	112

383 Table A.3 Frequency each policy intervention was studied

384 Policy packaging (i.e., considering the effect of more than 1 policy within a single scenario) was
385 observed 364 times (33.3%), in 134 studies (36.7%). For the remaining 728 policy scenarios
386 (66.7%), policy packaging was not considered, indicating a focus on the effect of one specific
387 policy for the scenario in 285 studies (76%). Note that the same studies can include policy
388 scenarios with and without packaging. Identified articles reported various outcomes, including
389 traffic emissions (77.9%), TRAP (38.0%), human exposures (12.0%) and health impacts
390 (13.3%). However, only 3% of articles reported all elements of the full-chain (Khreis, 2020)
391 covering an assessment of traffic emissions, TRAP, human exposures, and health impacts.

392 The sections below summarize evidence under the 6 overarching policy categories (Table S.5).

393 *Pricing Policies*

394 Pricing policies refer to policies that involve a monetary charge, tax, price increase, fee, or
395 incentive. Specifically, the 8 pricing policies considered in this SEM include air pollution
396 charging fees, congestion charging, fuel taxes or price increase, mileage-based user fees, parking
397 charges, road pricing, pricing incentives, and vehicle ownership taxes. In total, pricing policies
398 were studied 192 times, with the two most studied instruments being parking charges (55 times)
399 and road pricing (51 times) (Table A.3).

400 Air pollution charging fees refer to actions such as an emissions-based motor tax. Congestion
401 charging refers to road charges that aim to reduce congestion. Fuel taxes or price increase refers
402 to fuel taxation or intentional increases in fuel prices. Mileage-based user fees refer to road
403 pricing based on distance traveled. Parking charges refer to fees for parking. Road pricing refers
404 to actions such as cordon pricing, toll rings, area licensing schemes, and high occupancy toll

405 lanes. Vehicle ownership taxes refer to imposing a tax on vehicle purchases. Unlike the previous
406 penalty approaches, the pricing incentive policy was studied 23 times and refers to actions such
407 as reducing bus fares and monetary incentives for the purchase of "green" vehicles. We note,
408 however, that other pricing policies documented in the literature are missing from this SEM.
409 These policies include for example and concessionary fares, which is documented in KonSULT
410 (University of Leeds, 2016).

411 *Land-use Policies*

412 Land-use policies refer to policies that focus on development and planning. The 6 land-use
413 policies considered in this SEM include development density and mixed developments, parking
414 expansion, superblock development, transit-oriented development, urban sprawl, and urban
415 transport planning. In total, land-use policies were studied 77 times, with development density
416 and mixed developments being studied the most (42 times), followed by transit-oriented
417 development (18 times) (Table A.3).

418 Development density and mixed developments refers to policies that support increased
419 centralization and mixed development. Parking expansion refers to increased parking space.
420 Superblock development refers to multiblock grids that prioritize cyclist and pedestrian use over
421 cars. Transit-oriented development refers to public transit focused land use. Urban sprawl refers
422 to policies that support increased decentralization including limited land development controls
423 and rapid expansion of utility service areas. Urban transport planning refers to the planning
424 process in which policies, goals, etc. are assessed for transportation. Developer contributions to
425 infrastructure, which is documented as land-use policy in KonSULT (University of Leeds, 2016),
426 is missing from this SEM. Developer contributions involve a developer providing a payment (or
427 levy) to support infrastructure in the area they develop based on the understanding that new
428 developments will impose new burdens on existing infrastructure.

429 *Infrastructure Policies*

430 Infrastructure policies refer to policies that relate to the built environment. The 11 infrastructure
431 policies considered in this SEM include active transportation infrastructure, bus rapid transit or
432 mass rapid transit, greenspace or blue space, park-and-ride, public transportation infrastructure,
433 roadway development, solid roadside barrier, speed bump development, street ventilation,
434 unconventional intersection or intersection alteration, and vegetative roadside barrier, surface, or
435 roof. In total, infrastructure policies were studied 197 times. Bus or mass rapid transit were
436 studied the most (34 times), followed by public transportation infrastructure (31 times).

437 Active transportation infrastructure refers to structures like pedestrian or bike lanes. Bus rapid
438 transit or mass rapid transit refers to policies that supported rapid transit infrastructure
439 development. Greenspace or blue space development refers to the development of spaces like
440 parks with trees and ponds. Park-and-ride refers to parking areas with public transportation
441 connections. Public transportation infrastructure refers to the extension or improvement of transit
442 infrastructure including for example, bus-only lanes or new tram lines. Roadway development

443 may refer to freeway development, lane reduction, street re-pavement, road improvement, or the
444 creation of a bypass or high-speed street. Solid roadside barriers refer to concrete or other solid
445 barriers placed near a road. Speed bump development refers to traffic calming devices such as a
446 speed hump. Street ventilation refers to the removal of buildings for street ventilation through
447 open and staggered street canopy layouts (commonly seen in Taipei city). Unconventional
448 intersections or intersection alterations include roundabouts and median U-turns. Vegetative
449 roadside barriers, surfaces, or roofs refer to structures like green walls and green roofs placed
450 near a road.

451 *Behavioral Policies*

452 Behavioral policies refer to policies that involve a change in individuals' behavior or practices.
453 The 4 behavioral policies considered in this SEM include flexible work arrangements which
454 includes e- or telecommuting, the promotion or shift to active/non-motorized transport, public
455 transit, and ride sharing. In total, behavioral policies were studied 116 times, with public transit
456 promotion or shift being studied the most (47 times).

457 Flexible work arrangements refer to work from home or hybrid work arrangements where
458 workers may work remotely. Active or non-motorized transport promotion or shift refers to
459 increased walking or biking transport methods. Public transit promotion or shift may include
460 increased public transit usage through incentives. Ride-sharing promotion or shift refers to
461 practices such as carpooling or car-sharing via services such as Uber or Lyft. While company
462 travel plans were included in this SEM (Nelson et al., 2007, Wall et al., 2017), school travel
463 plans or school mobility management policies and personalized journey planning (which falls
464 under the umbrella of public awareness campaigns) are missing. Also, bike sharing is missing.

465 *Technology Policies*

466 Technology policies refer to policies that implement innovative and technological advances. The
467 8 technology policies considered in this SEM include alternative fuel technology, alternative
468 vehicle technology, electronic toll technology, material coating, real-time passenger information,
469 speed control technology, stop/start technology, and vehicle retrofitting. In total, technology
470 policies were studied 399 times, the second largest overarching category studied (after
471 Management, Standards, and Service Policies, described next), with alternative fuel technology
472 being studied the most (265 times).

473 Alternative fuel technology includes electric vehicles (EVs), biodiesel, and hybrid technology.
474 Alternative vehicle technology includes connected and autonomous vehicle technology. Notably,
475 shared autonomous vehicles were considered as both alternative vehicle technology and ride-
476 sharing promotion or shift policies, where they were presented as such (for example, the study of
477 autonomous taxis or aTaxis presented in Fagnant and Kockelman (2014)). Electronic toll
478 technology refers to electronic toll collection capabilities. Material coating refers to
479 photocatalytic paint, A9 material, pervious pavement, titanium dioxide, and photocatalytic
480 nanoparticles as road coating. Real-time passenger information, which was studied the least (2

481 times), includes dial-a-ride service. Speed control technology includes active accelerator pedals.
482 Stop/start technology refers to a system that turns an engine off when a vehicle is stationary.
483 Vehicle retrofitting encompasses diesel particulate filters (DPFs), diesel oxidation catalysts
484 (DOCs), catalytic converters (CACs), and exhaust gas recirculation (EGR). Of note is that other
485 literature considers real-time passenger information as an information provision policy in the
486 same category as, for example, crowdsourcing, in-vehicle and parking guidance systems
487 (University of Leeds, 2016). The following policy interventions are missing from this SEM:
488 conventional and variable signs and markings, crowdsourcing and barrier-free mobility.

489 *Management, Standards, and Services Policies*

490 Management, standards, and services policies refer to policies that relate to regulations,
491 restrictions, optimization, or other established rules. The 21 policies considered under this
492 category include fleet management, fuel regulation or restriction, high occupancy vehicle lane,
493 inspection and maintenance program, intelligent transport system, low emission zone (LEZ),
494 loading, unloading, and/or idling regulation, parking standards, reduction, or regulation, public
495 transport expansion, public transport regulation, speed limit regulation or reduction, street
496 cleaning, studded tire regulation, traffic signal optimization, vehicle or manufacturing alteration,
497 vehicle emission regulation, vehicle purchase restriction, vehicle rerouting or route optimization,
498 vehicle retirement or replacement, vehicle shift, and vehicle use restriction. Management,
499 standards, and services policies were studied 783 times representing 72% of the time, with
500 vehicle emissions regulation being the most studied (126 times).

501 Fleet management included freight demand management, off-hour deliveries, consolidated goods
502 distribution center, nighttime construction, left turn prohibitions, traffic demand control, road
503 capacity limitations, and freight transport optimization. Fuel regulation or restriction refers to the
504 ban of leaded gasoline and fuel quality standards. High occupancy vehicle lane refers to lanes
505 that may only be used by a vehicle with 2 or more passengers. Inspection and maintenance
506 program facilitates the identification of potentially high emitting in-service vehicles through
507 routine inspection. Intelligent transport system refers to eco-driving and intelligent speed
508 adaptation systems. LEZ refers to regulations placed on an area that prevent high emitting
509 vehicles from driving through. Loading, unloading, and/or idling regulation refers to restrictions
510 that limit vehicle idling time. Parking standards, reductions, or regulations refer to actions like
511 reduced parking. Public transport expansion refers to increased transit services such as longer
512 routes or more frequent service levels. Public transport regulation refers to limiting bus stops,
513 optimizing commuter trains, regulating bus speed, and regulating transit travel time. Speed limit
514 regulation refers to speed limit reductions or increases. Street cleaning refers to services that
515 clear roadways of various debris for example, by vacuum cleaning and spraying water on city
516 streets (Shen et al., 2008, Goyal et al., 2019). Studded tire regulation limits studded tire use.
517 Traffic signal optimization refers to traffic signal control or coordination. Vehicle or
518 manufacturing alteration includes the production of more aerodynamic cars (for example, mass
519 and drag reduction), as well as requirements for drayage trucks to be equipped with newer

520 engines. Vehicle emission regulation includes emission standards (i.e., Euro IV, Euro III, etc.)
 521 and controls. Vehicle purchase restriction includes the license plate lottery which specifies a
 522 fixed quantity of vehicle purchase permits per year. Vehicle rerouting or route optimization
 523 refers to street closures or traffic circulation plans that aim to reroute traffic to less busy streets.
 524 Vehicle retirement or replacement refers to vehicle phase-outs and fleet renewals. Vehicle shift
 525 refers to the vehicle demand shift that occurs when no additional two-stroke motorcycles are
 526 introduced to the market, for example. Vehicle use restriction includes odd-even schemes,
 527 vehicle bans, and restricting traffic during certain times of the day.

528 *Methods Used to Assess Impact*

529 Included articles implemented different methods including measurement or modeling techniques
 530 while some articles implemented both methods to assess the impact of policy scenarios. 503
 531 policy scenarios (46.1%) in 135 unique articles exclusively utilized modeling. 79 policy
 532 scenarios (7.2%) in 41 unique articles exclusively utilized measurement, and 510 policy
 533 scenarios (46.7%) in 189 unique articles utilized both modeling and measurement methods.

534 *Geographic Location*

535 The 1,092 policy scenarios were investigated across a total of 50 countries. Most policy
 536 scenarios were investigated in China, followed by the United States, United Kingdom, India, and
 537 Spain (Table A.5). The remaining countries considered less than 60 policy scenarios each and
 538 include Portugal (5.4%), Mexico (4.9%), Brazil (3.6%), Italy (3.3%), Canada (3.0%), Lebanon
 539 (2.7%), Germany (2.1%), France (2.1%), Greece (2.1%), Iran (2.0%), Israel (1.5%), Netherlands
 540 (1.3%), Lithuania (1.2%), Ireland (1.1%), Thailand (1.1%), and Belgium (1.0%). Furthermore,
 541 the following countries were considered for < 1.0% of all policy scenarios: Indonesia, Chile,
 542 Japan, Australia, Philippines, Taiwan, Ecuador, Finland, Hong Kong, Sweden, Colombia, Egypt,
 543 South Africa, Austria, Denmark, South Korea, Macedonia, Poland, Bangladesh, Switzerland,
 544 Norway, New Zealand, Serbia, Vietnam, Czech Republic, Hungary, Jordan, Qatar, and Slovenia.
 545 Notably, 41 policy scenarios (3.8%) did not have a defined country denoted in the article and
 546 were marked as “N/A” in the final Excel database. From a continental perspective, 453 policy
 547 scenarios were studied in Europe, followed by 320 in Asia, 206 in North America, 57 in South
 548 America, 8 in Africa, and 7 in Australia.

Country	Frequency Studied (%)
China	138 (12.6%)
United States	119 (10.9%)
United Kingdom	93 (8.5%)
India	87 (8.0%)
Spain	83 (7.6%)

549 Table A.5 Most frequently studied countries

550 For city/urban areas, 221 unique locations were documented for the included articles. Twelve
 551 policy scenarios investigated multiple cities simultaneously while the remaining 1,080 scenarios

552 were investigated in one urban area specifically. The urban area studied most was London where
553 78 policy scenarios were investigated (7.1%) in 11 unique articles, followed by Beijing with 60
554 scenarios (5.5%) investigated in 20 unique articles, Mexico City with 54 scenarios (4.9%)
555 investigated in 11 unique articles, Madrid with 45 scenarios (4.1%) investigated in 14 unique
556 articles, Delhi with 44 scenarios (4.0%) investigated in 15 unique articles, Beirut with 30
557 scenarios (2.7%) investigated in 3 unique articles, and Barcelona with 30 scenarios (2.7%)
558 investigated in 12 unique articles. In addition to the cities listed above, New York City, Milan,
559 and Guangzhou were studied the most based on the number of unique articles (12, 8 and 6,
560 respectively). The remaining urban areas were studied < 2% each of all policy scenarios.
561 Notably, 70 policy scenarios (6.4%) did not have a defined urban area denoted in the article and
562 were marked as “N/A” in the final Excel database. For example, some of these studies modeled a
563 policy scenario using urban data but did not specify which urban area (i.e., New York City,
564 London, etc.). While a specific city was not named, the use of urban data to reflect an urban
565 environment met our inclusion criteria, and hence, those studies were included.

566 *Analysis Years*

567 The start analysis year and end analysis year were captured for each policy scenario. Start
568 analysis years ranged from 1974 to 2030. End analysis years ranged from 1996 to 2050. The
569 longest gap between analysis years was 50 years which started in 2000 and ended in 2050 and
570 occurred in 16 policy scenarios. The shortest gap between analysis years was 0 years indicating
571 the same start and end year which occurred in 288 policy scenarios. Notably, 191 policy
572 scenarios (17%) did not have defined analysis years in the article and were marked as “N/A” in
573 the final Excel database.

574 *Pollutants Considered*

575 Twenty-five traffic pollutants were identified in the included articles: ammonia (NH₃), BC, black
576 smoke (BS), CO, EC, HC, NO, NO₂, NO_x, organic carbon (OC), particulate matter with a
577 diameter equal to or less than 1 micrometer (PM₁), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, PM_{absorbance}, PM_x, reactive
578 organic gases (ROG), respirable suspended particulate matter (RSPM), secondary organic
579 aerosols (SOA), SO₂, sulfur oxides (SO_x), suspended particulate matter (SPM), total carbon
580 (TC), total organic gases (TOG), UFP, and VOC. Traffic pollutants that were not specified were
581 referred to as “Other” in the final Excel database and represent a twenty-sixth category. For
582 example, one study reported the effect of green roofs on pollutant concentrations but did not
583 specify the pollutants involved (Baik et al., 2012). The most frequently studied pollutants include
584 NO_x (234 unique articles), CO (177 unique articles), PM₁₀ (109 unique articles), HC (101 unique
585 articles), and PM_{2.5} (95 unique articles), which were studied in 61.6%, 50.0%, 33.8%, 27.4%, and
586 21.9% of policy scenarios, respectively. The remaining pollutants were studied in less than 20%
587 of all policy scenarios, for example, NO₂ was studied in 17.7% of policy scenarios or 68 unique
588 articles. The least frequently studied pollutants were PM_{absorbance}, SOA, and TC, which were only
589 studied in 1 policy scenario each.

590 *Primary Outcomes: Changes in Traffic Emissions and TRAP*

591 The effect on traffic emissions was reported in 851 of the policy scenarios (77.9%)
592 corresponding to 266 unique articles (72.6%). Figure A.2 displays traffic emissions effects
593 reported by each pollutant studied in the 851 policy scenarios. The pollutants most frequently
594 studied for traffic emissions effects were NO_x, CO, HC, PM₁₀, and SO₂ at 621, 501, 294, 245,
595 and 143 times, respectively. A reduction in emissions was most frequently reported (2,064 times
596 across all pollutants) although emission increases (238 times), mixed effects (i.e., both reduction
597 and increase observed: 27 times), and no changes (i.e., stayed the same: 59 times) were also
598 observed. Notably, NO_x emissions were reported to have increased in 83 policy scenarios,
599 followed by CO and HC; reported to increase in 50 and 38 policy scenarios, respectively.

600 The effect on ambient concentrations of TRAP was reported in 415 of the policy scenarios
601 (38.0%) corresponding to 154 unique articles (42%). Figure A.3 displays TRAP effects reported
602 by each pollutant studied in the 415 policy scenarios. The pollutants most frequently studied for
603 TRAP effects were PM₁₀, NO₂, PM_{2.5}, NO_x, and CO at 208, 157, 156, 65, and 49 times,
604 respectively. A reduction in TRAP was most frequently (650 times across all pollutants) reported
605 although TRAP increases (71 times), mixed effects (i.e., both reduction and increase observed:
606 50 times), and no changes (i.e., stayed the same: 30 times) were also observed. Notably, NO₂
607 concentrations were reported to have increased in 17 policy scenarios, followed by PM₁₀ and
608 PM_{2.5}; reported to increase in 11 and 9 policy scenarios, respectively.

609

Traffic Emission Effects by Pollutant

610

611 Figure A.2 Traffic Emission Effects and Pollutants Reported

TRAP Effects by Pollutant

612

613 Figure A.3 TRAP Effects and Pollutants Reported

614 *Secondary Outcomes: Human Exposures and Health Impacts*

615 Human exposures were reported in 12.0% of (131) policy scenarios corresponding to 31 unique
616 articles (8.5%). Of the articles that reported human exposure effects, PM₁₀ (79 times) was the
617 most frequently studied pollutant, followed by PM_{2.5} (50 times), and only 10 pollutant categories
618 out of the 26 included in the database were studied. Health impacts were reported in 13.3% of
619 (145) policy scenarios corresponding to 36 unique articles (9.9%). Like human exposures, PM₁₀
620 (96 times) was the most frequently studied pollutant, followed by PM_{2.5} (52 times), and only 8
621 pollutant categories out of the 26 included in the full database were studied for their health
622 impacts. The other pollutants studied for their health impacts in order of frequency were NO₂ (15
623 times), NO_x (8 times), CO (3 times), EC and SO₂ (2 times each), and VOC (1 time). Various
624 health impacts were reported including activity effects (e.g., restricted activity days), allergy
625 effects, cancer, cardiovascular effects, cerebrovascular effects, disability-adjusted life years
626 (DALYs), hospitalization, metabolic outcomes, neurological or cognitive disorders, premature
627 mortality, and respiratory effects. Both mortality and morbidity were studied, primarily in health
628 impact assessment studies of various scenarios, sometimes combined with economic valuation
629 (e.g., (Rodrigues et al., 2020, Dey et al., 2018, Malina and Scheffler, 2015, Wadud and Khan,
630 2013). The most frequently reported health impacts were premature mortality, which was
631 reported 133 times, followed by respiratory effects at 30 times, cardiovascular effects at 22
632 times, and DALYs at 18 times. The least frequently reported health impact was allergy effects,
633 which were only reported once, followed by metabolic outcomes and neurological or cognitive
634 disorders which were each reported 3 times.

635 *Secondary Items of Interest: Enablers, Barriers, and Co-benefits*

636 Enablers to policy intervention implementation were reported a total of 3 times in 3 unique
637 articles. Financial, public opinion, and technological enablers were each reported once. Barriers
638 to policy intervention implementation were reported a total of 191 times in 35 unique articles.
639 Behavioral, financial, governance/legislation/politics, infrastructural, knowledge/skills, public
640 opinion, land-use, and technological barriers were all reported. The most frequent barrier
641 documented was financial barriers which were reported 124 times, followed by
642 governance/legislation/politics barriers at 29 times, and infrastructural barriers at 16 times.
643 Barriers were referred to as limiting conditions, challenges, and resistance. Co-benefits were
644 reported a total of 988 times in 199 unique articles. The 19 documented co-benefits included
645 economic growth or savings, job growth, increased accessibility, increased active transportation,
646 increased greenspace, increased network speed, increased petrol savings, increased safety,
647 increased social welfare, increased transit use, reduced energy or fuel consumption, reduced
648 GHG emissions/climate change mitigation, reduced health costs, reduced number of trips,
649 reduced traffic congestion, reduced trip time or length, reduced traffic noise, reduced heat or
650 urban heat island, and reduced vehicle miles (or kilometers) traveled. The most frequently
651 reported co-benefit was reduced GHG emissions/climate change mitigation which was reported
652 in 325 policy scenarios (29.7%). Other frequently reported co-benefits included reduced vehicle
653 miles (or kilometers) traveled which was reported 114 times, followed by reduced energy or fuel

654 consumption at 92 times, economic growth or savings at 86 times, reduced traffic congestion at
655 76 times and reduced trip times or length at 75 times. Increased active transportation and
656 increased safety were each reported 31 times while increased transit use was reported 31 times.
657 Increased accessibility, reduced health costs, job growth, increased social welfare, increased
658 greenspace, increased petrol savings and reduced traffic noise and heat/urban heat island were all
659 reported 10 times or less.

660 *Open-access Excel Database*

661 The data collected for included studies are hosted in an open-access Microsoft Excel sheet
662 database which is query-able by use of the filter, sort/order, search functions, and the Power
663 Query tool so users may identify and access specific information of interest. Information in the
664 Excel database comes from the 365 included articles and the 1,092 policy scenarios within. This
665 information may be searched across different data items including urban-level policy
666 intervention, publication year, study type, policy packaging, methods used, population
667 characteristics including age, gender, race, and sample size where relevant, geographic location,
668 analysis years, pollutants studied, and primary outcomes (traffic emissions and/or TRAP) and
669 their direction of effect, secondary outcomes (human exposures and health impacts), and
670 secondary items of interest (enablers and barriers to intervention implementation and co-
671 benefits). The Excel database includes 4 worksheets (tabs). The first worksheet is the
672 Introduction which details the purpose of the SEM. The second worksheet is the Codebook
673 which contains information for each variable coded in the database. The third sheet is the Master
674 Sheet which contains all information extracted for the 365 articles included. Note the Entry ID
675 column references the entry number and corresponds to each policy scenario documented
676 whereas the Article ID column indicates which article the policy scenarios correspond to. For
677 example, entries 1-3 correspond to article 1 which means that the first article listed in the Excel
678 database investigated 3 separate policy scenarios. Finally, the fourth sheet contains ready-to-go
679 queries users may find helpful. We specifically queried information for the following questions:

- 680 1. How often was policy packaging studied?
- 681 2. How often was each policy intervention and policy category studied?
- 682 3. How often were different methods (modeling and measurement) used?
- 683 4. How often were different countries and continents studied?
- 684 5. How often were different traffic pollutants studied?
- 685 6. How often were traffic emission effects reported and what was the distribution of effects
686 observed for different pollutants across emissions reduction, increase, mixed effect, and
687 no change?
- 688 7. How often were TRAP effects reported and what was the distribution of effects observed
689 for different pollutants across TRAP reduction, increase, mixed effect, and no change?
- 690 8. How often were human exposures reported and what pollutants were studied?
- 691 9. How often were health impacts reported, what type of health impacts were reported, and
692 what pollutants were studied?

- 693 10. How often were different policy enablers and barriers reported?
- 694 11. How often were different co-benefits reported?
- 695 12. What proportion of articles investigate all elements of the full-chain linking traffic
- 696 activity to human health (traffic emissions, TRAP, exposures, and health impacts)?

697 These are ready-to-go queries for ease of use, but users can analyze the data based on their
 698 questions of interest. Our intended users are researchers and urban authorities, such as cities, air
 699 agencies, local authorities including county and district councils, and metropolitan planning
 700 organizations (MPOs) or districts. We encourage this audience to use the Excel database to
 701 identify information on various urban-level policy interventions implemented around the world
 702 to reduce traffic emissions and TRAP, and potentially yield benefits to human exposures and
 703 health and a wide range of documented social, environmental, climate and economic outcomes.

704 *Open Access Interactive Visualization Tool*

705 Finally, the Excel database was then used to create interactive data visualizations using Tableau.
 706 The dashboard represents information for the 365 articles and 1,092 policy scenarios included in
 707 the SEM. Users may query the data according to different topics of interest. The dashboard is
 708 divided into five sections as described below.

709 *Section 1* is a set of Pie charts displaying the proportion of policy scenarios which report traffic
 710 emissions, TRAP, exposures, and health effects and impacts. Click on "Yes" or "No" in each pie
 711 chart to filter the studies associated with it as shown in Figure A.4.

712
 713 Figure A.4. Screenshot of Section 1 of Tableau Dashboard for interactively visualizing the SEM database

714 Section 2 is a geographic map which displays the frequency of policy scenarios studied in each
 715 country. Click on a country to filter the studies associated with it as shown in Figure A.5.

716

717 Figure A.5. Screenshot of Section 2 of Tableau Dashboard for interactively visualizing the SEM database

718 *Section 3* displays the characteristics selected from a dropdown box. The user can click on
 719 specific categories in the dropdown box to filter the studies associated with it as shown in Figure
 720 A.6. The dropdown box lets the user choose a visual based on the following parameters:

- 721 1. Policy Interventions: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each policy
 722 intervention
- 723 2. Pollutants Studied: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each pollutant studied
- 724 3. Health Effects and Impacts: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each health
 725 effect and impact
- 726 4. Policy Enablers: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each policy enabler
- 727 5. Policy Barriers: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each policy barrier
- 728 6. Co-benefits: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each co-benefit
- 729 7. Analysis Start and End Years: Frequency of policy scenarios that document each start
 730 and end analysis year
- 731 8. Publication Years: Frequency of articles that were published each year
- 732 9. Scientific Journals: Frequency of articles that were published in each scientific journal

733

734 Figure A.6. Screenshot of Section 3 of Tableau Dashboard for interactively visualizing the SEM database

735 Section 4 is a combination of visuals showing the effect of selected policy in Section 3 on the
 736 traffic emissions and ambient concentrations of TRAP for the different pollutants as shown in
 737 Figure A.7. The user can click on a specific direction to filter the studies associated with it.

738

739 Figure A.7. Screenshot of Section 4 of Tableau Dashboard for interactively visualizing the SEM database

740 Section 5 finally lists the articles associated with selected filters in Sections 1 to 4 as shown in
 741 Figure A.8. Click on a reference to be redirected to the article page.

Article List	
Agarwal et al. 2020	Bicycle superhighway: An environmentally sustainable policy for urban transport
Aggarwal and Jain 2015	Impact of air pollutants from surface transport sources on human health: A modeling and epidemiological approach
Ahanchian and Biona 2014	Energy demand, emissions forecasts and mitigation strategies modeled over a medium-range horizon: The case of the land transportation...
Ahmad and Dewan 2007	Electric vehicle: a futuristic approach to reduce pollution (A case study of Delhi)
Al-Rousan et al. 2015	Urban traffic pollution reduction for sedan cars using petrol engines by hydro-oxide gas inclusion
Alam et al. 2014a	A simulation of transit bus emissions along an urban corridor: Evaluating changes under various service improvement strategies
Alam et al. 2014b	Traffic Emissions and Air Quality Near Roads in Dense Urban Neighborhood: Using Microscopic Simulation for Evaluating Effects of Vehicle Fleet, Travel Demand, and Road Network Changes
Amann et al. 2017	Managing future air quality in megacities: A case study for Delhi

742

743 Figure A.8. Screenshot of Section 5 of Tableau Dashboard for interactively visualizing the SEM database

744 The dashboard is hosted on Texas A&M’s Transportation Institute’s Tableau server:

745 https://tableau.tamu.edu/t/TTI/views/SEMDataVisualizationV2/SEMVisualizationDashboard?showAppBanner=false&:display_count=n&:showVizHome=n&:origin=viz_share_link

746

747 *Use of Interactive Visualization Tool to find Policy Intervention Impacts*

748 This interactive visualization tool can help users dig deeper into the impact of policy
 749 interventions on primary outcomes (traffic emissions/TRAP), secondary outcomes (human
 750 exposures and health impacts), and explore enablers, barriers, and co-benefits in specific areas.
 751 For example, we used the dashboard to filter studies which reported TRAP in Section 1 by
 752 clicking on “Yes” under the “TRAP Reported” Pie chart. We then clicked on “Poland” in Section
 753 2, to find out that only the policy “vehicle retirement or replacement” was studied in two policy
 754 scenarios as shown in Section 3. No health outcomes, policy enablers, barriers or co-benefits
 755 were reported on, and analysis years were 2000 and 2030. The effect seen was a reduction in
 756 ambient concentrations of NO₂ and PM₁₀ in both policy scenarios, as shown in Section 4. This
 757 was studied in one article: Giannouli et al. (2011), as shown in Section 5. We then clicked on the
 758 article and were redirected to its webpage. We found that the authors modeled the impact of a
 759 Maximum Feasible Reductions (MFR) scenario which assumes full implementation of the most
 760 advanced technical measures to reduce emissions, but their scenario did not consider the
 761 retirement of existing equipment before the end of its technical lifetime. This scenario was
 762 predicted to reduce NO₂ street increments for narrow canyons from 16-53 µg/m³ to 7-24 µg/m³.
 763 The corresponding range for PM₁₀ was estimated to be 5-15 µg/m³ for the reference year and 0.2-
 764 2.4 µg/m³ for the MFR scenario. These reductions correspond to 55%-56% for NO₂ and for 84%-
 765 96% PM₁₀ in this modeling study. Users can follow these steps to find out more about any policy
 766 scenario in any area of interest.

767 **DISCUSSION**

768 Following a published protocol (Sanchez et al., 2020), this SEM synthesizes peer-reviewed
 769 studies on urban policy interventions to reduce traffic emissions and/or TRAP from across the
 770 globe. The 365 included articles contained within them a total of 1,092 policy scenarios which
 771 were examined and characterized in a pre-defined and standardized manner. As such, this SEM:
 772 1. unites a complex and disparate evidence base, 2. facilitates the identification of patterns and

773 gaps in the literature and 3. serves as the foundation for future research, practice, and policy
774 recommendations. The results of this SEM have been used to produce a tool of both research and
775 practical significance, via an open-access, query-able Excel database, and an interactive
776 visualization tool. These tools are intended as resources for researchers and practitioners which
777 could undergo future development and updates. Below, we discuss our findings and the strengths
778 and limitations of this work.

779 Much evidence on this topic has emerged over the last decade and continues to emerge, which
780 emphasizes the importance of traffic emission and TRAP mitigation through urban- and city-
781 level policies and perhaps the increasingly important role of cities in combating air pollution and
782 climate change. There were 58 unique policies reported and synthesized which provide a large
783 range of appropriate options for practitioners and policy makers to consider in their work,
784 including options beyond pre-conceived and trialed ideas or those traditionally deployed in a
785 particular setting. The most frequently studied overarching policy categories were management,
786 standards, and services and then technology while the least studied were behavioral and land-use,
787 indicating research gaps in assessing the impacts of changing behaviors, land-use, and urban
788 development patterns. We also noted that some policy instruments identified in our initial
789 scoping using KonSULT were missing from our synthesized evidence base including school
790 travel plans, school mobility management, personalized journey planning, bike sharing,
791 developer contributions, concessionary fares, conventional and variable signs and markings,
792 crowdsourcing and barrier-free mobility.

793 Notably, there was much less reporting of policy interventions' effects on TRAP (38.0%)
794 compared to traffic emissions (77.9%). There were even less reports of human exposure (12.0%)
795 and health effects or impacts (13.3%) in the included studies, indicating that most studies
796 conclude their assessment before assessing human exposure and health implications. A mere 3%
797 of articles reported on all elements of the full-chain from traffic emissions, TRAP, human
798 exposures, and health effects or impacts (Khreis, 2020). Increased investigation of human
799 exposures and health effects or impacts in this context is warranted, especially to understand if
800 an emissions reduction policy will ultimately have a beneficial health outcome.

801 This relative lack of research and evidence is likely a function of both siloes between
802 transportation and health disciplines in research and practice, as well as the nature of how air
803 quality policy is implemented. While the goal of most air quality improvement policies is to
804 protect and enhance the public's health, it is generally the vehicle emissions that are regulated
805 with the assumption that any emissions reduction will result in a public health improvement. The
806 quantification of health effects or impacts, and their associated economic costs may encourage
807 the adoption of certain policy interventions if they are seen to provide additional incentive
808 beyond environmental improvements of less emissions (or ambient air pollution). We found that
809 very few studies utilized measurements to assess effects of policy interventions, and they mostly
810 examined alternative fuel technology, and vehicle emissions regulation. This could be ascribed to

811 the complexity and high costs of measurement campaigns and pre- and post-assessments, and
812 their follow-up.

813 The pollutants studied generally reflected specific markers for traffic activity; for example, NO_x
814 was the pollutant most studied, however, other specific markers like EC, BC, and UFPs are not
815 well-represented in the literature. PM_{2.5}, a pollutant with well-established health effects is
816 investigated more than EC and NO₂, which are both emerging as key traffic-related air
817 pollutants, with adverse health effects related to respiratory outcomes in both children and adults,
818 diabetes, and mortality (HEI, 2022). Although traffic emissions and TRAP were predominantly
819 reduced in the policy scenarios studied, the reductions did not result in air quality that always
820 met air quality standards. Some studies may observe improvements in air quality, but air
821 pollution might still be above the recommended levels (Taksibi et al., 2020; Tomassetti et al.,
822 2020). Studies also showed emissions and TRAP increases, most notably for NO_x and NO₂,
823 respectively. NO_x emissions and NO₂ concentrations seemed to increase predominantly in
824 studies of alternative fuel technology, speed bump development and intelligent transport
825 systems. It is, however, important to consider that this trend in the literature may be a result of
826 publication bias where studies showing reduction in traffic emissions and TRAP are more likely
827 to be published, than those showing no changes or increases in these outcomes.

828 Another consideration is policy packaging. One-third of policy scenarios were documented as
829 policy packages since the scenario studied the effect of multiple policy interventions at the same
830 time. Different policy combinations may impact traffic emissions and TRAP effects differently
831 than when implemented individually. Such scenarios reflect real-world situations where more
832 than one policy may be implemented in an area at a time; for example, during special events such
833 as the Olympic Games where traffic is anticipated to be much higher than normal in an urban
834 area. Some papers indicated that policy packages tended to be more effective at reducing
835 emissions/TRAP than when policies were considered separately.

836 Limited evidence was noted for certain policy interventions including vehicle ownership taxes,
837 parking expansion, superblock development, greenspace or blue space, street ventilation, real-
838 time passenger information, stop/start technology, studded tire regulations and vehicle shift.
839 These policy interventions require more research to better understand their effects on traffic
840 emissions and TRAP in an urban setting and they may have important implications. For example,
841 passengers using public transit that is often delayed or canceled but are unaware of these
842 disruptions in real-time due to the absence of real-time passenger information may eventually
843 switch to modes with better information and reliability, where they may have more control over
844 their schedules, such as taxis or private vehicles.

845 Regarding geographic location, policy interventions were studied least in Africa and Australia.
846 At the country-level, Jordan, Qatar, Czech Republic, Hungary, and Slovenia were studied the
847 least, highlighting a gap in Middle Eastern and Eastern European urban areas. Most of the
848 literature comes from Asia, Northern Europe, and North America. This is in line with the

849 research on the health effects of TRAP which remains very limited in Africa and the Middle East
850 (HEI, 2022). This is even though most population growth, urbanization and motorization will
851 occur in low- and middle-income countries. Most population growth is currently occurring in
852 China and India, while most projected increases are expected in Africa (Democratic Republic of
853 the Congo, Egypt, Ethiopia, Nigeria, and the United Republic of Tanzania) (United Nations
854 Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022). Also, currently, countries in Asia, Africa,
855 and the Middle East experience the highest ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations. For example, the
856 highest global population-weighted 2019 average PM_{2.5} exposures were in India, Nepal, Niger,
857 Qatar, and Nigeria (HEI, 2020).

858 Interestingly, enablers to policy intervention implementation were reported less frequently than
859 barriers. Potential explanations for this may be that barriers are more easily identifiable, more
860 prominent in policy discourse, or authors may be more willing or interested to report on barriers
861 rather than enablers. Certain enablers, whilst important, are completely missing from this SEM
862 including behavioral, knowledge and skills, legislation, and land-use. GHG emissions/climate
863 change mitigation was the single most reported co-benefit, highlighting its importance in current
864 discourse and its intersection with emissions and air pollution reduction goals. Climate change is
865 expected to further worsen air quality, where increasing intensity and frequency of heat waves
866 and stagnant air can result in poorer air quality and increase susceptibility and adverse health
867 effects. These trends and associated individual studies, and their findings, can be explored in
868 more detail though the Excel database and interactive visualization tool.

869 This work has some limitations, some attributable to the high volume of journal articles returned
870 in this area in comparison to other systematic review or evidence mapping efforts. First, study
871 screening was not fully conducted in duplicates due to time and resource restrictions. Only a
872 random 20% of studies were screened in duplicate, and any disagreements were resolved through
873 a third author. This is in line with our published protocol (Sanchez et al., 2020). KS and HK
874 reviewed the screening process and the data extraction and coding process at the outset and
875 selected papers were reviewed together to ensure all processes were well-defined and agreed
876 upon. We indicated which articles were among the 20% screened in duplicate at the title and
877 abstract level and full-text level, and we provided the agreement rate across those articles in the
878 Supplementary Material (Table S.3 and Table S.4). Agreement rate was high at the title and
879 abstract level (92.80%), and relatively smaller at the full-text level (88.50%), with a general
880 trend that KS, the primary reviewer, was more inclusive which indicates a good chance that we
881 did not exclude studies that should have been included. There were 14 conflicts between KS and
882 HK at the full-text level, 10 of those which KS included but HK chose to exclude (JB decision of
883 these studies was to include 1 and exclude 9). The other 4 studies KS excluded but HK chose to
884 include (JB decision of these studies was to include 1 and exclude 3). These discrepancies were
885 discussed upon identification and the reasons for discrepancies were identified and understood in
886 the hope of a better agreement with future screening.

887

888 We also excluded gray literature (i.e., books, book chapters, reports, etc.) from our search, due to
889 time and resource limitations, and the large number of returned records (Figure A.1). Although
890 in line with our published protocol (Sanchez et al., 2020), we acknowledge that this limits the
891 comprehensiveness of this SEM as relevant reports were not considered. In addition, it may
892 exacerbate the potential impact of publication bias which may be less pronounced in the gray
893 literature compared to peer-reviewed journal publications. In line with our protocol, there was no
894 quality assessment of the included studies although the purpose of this SEM was not
895 compromised (Sanchez et al., 2020). Users of our Excel database and interactive visualization
896 tool are recommended to critically assess study methods and findings before applying study
897 findings to their cases of interest. Our last searches were in June 2020. The increasing number of
898 studies in recent years suggests a need to update this SEM periodically to capture new urban
899 policy interventions and understand their impacts in a proactive manner which could benefit
900 policy and practice. While already slightly outdated, the explicit, detailed, and transparent
901 reporting of our methods, and our open-access Excel database, can facilitate updates to this SEM
902 in the future, and we would be interested in doing so if we secure required resources. Finally, our
903 database was produced in Excel format rather than a "relational" database that might identify
904 connections between data more efficiently – this was due to time, resource, and skill limitations.
905 However, we think potential users will be more familiar with Excel and how to navigate
906 it/perform different functions compared to a relational database. We complemented the Excel
907 database with an interactive visualization tool which enables easier and more visual
908 identification of underlying data and trends. There is also some overlap with categories in the
909 Excel database which may lend itself to a distorted picture of the evidence. For example, non-
910 methane hydrocarbons are technically both a HC and a VOC but were documented as only a HC
911 in the database due to Excel limitations and for simplicity. Although there is not much overlap
912 like the one just described, it is important to note this for users who may come across it.

913
914 Nonetheless, our SEM provides a valuable picture of the evidence base, searching a variety of
915 databases and producing open-access user-friendly outputs aimed at researchers, practitioners,
916 and policy makers. We followed a published protocol and adhered to it with very minor
917 amendments listed in full in Table S.7 in the Supplementary Material. If there were uncertainties
918 during study screening for any of the 80% of articles that were not screened in duplicate, another
919 author (HK) was consulted. This allowed for a structured way of discussing any unclear cases
920 with another reviewer and added an extra level of certainty for difficult articles that did not fall
921 within the 20% of articles screened in duplicate. Discrepancies for data coding were resolved
922 through consensus between KS and three reviewers (HK, TR, JB). We also included "Raw data"
923 columns in the Excel database as evidence to why certain codes were listed (for example, urban
924 policy interventions have a raw data column in addition to the column with codes so users can
925 have a better understanding of the policy/policies that were coded in the original authors'
926 language). This raw data column provides more detail and nuance to the users.

927

928 This SEM can address some of the principal weaknesses in policy option generation and
929 selection: an over-reliance on preconceived ideas; an unwillingness to consider measures for
930 which the responsibility lies with other bodies; a tendency to consider measures which are more
931 easily funded or more likely to be acceptable; a resulting focus on supply-side measures such as
932 infrastructure and management rather than demand-side measures such as regulation and pricing;
933 a lack of awareness of the wider range of policy measures available; and a lack of evidence of
934 the performance of those measures in other contexts (May et al., 2018). This work follows and
935 furthers our previous work which qualitatively and non-systematically assessed the potential
936 health impacts of different transport policy interventions (Khreis et al., 2017b). In this work,
937 however, we focus on one of the pathways between transport and health (Glazener et al., 2021),
938 TRAP, which allows us a much more detailed assessment and the inclusion of evidence of the
939 performance including case studies from around the world.

940

941 Future works might address items that were beyond the scope of the current SEM. For example,
942 this SEM excluded articles that were proxies for policy interventions like COVID-19 lockdowns
943 (Sharma et al., 2020; Sicard et al., 2020), but we, however, are systematically reviewing these
944 elsewhere with a focus on air pollution changes in low- and middle-income countries
945 (Navaratnam et al., 2022). Additionally, several articles exclusively investigated policy
946 intervention effects on GHG; a secondary item of interest (Souche-Le Corvec et al., 2019). And
947 several articles exclusively focused on exposure and health effects (Estrella et al., 2019), or
948 impacts (secondary outcomes) as related to traffic emissions and TRAP so did not meet our
949 criteria of reporting on our primary outcomes. While these studies were beyond our pre-defined
950 scope, such articles still provide valuable information for traffic emission and TRAP reduction
951 potential as well as exposure and health benefits. Another item for future works to consider is
952 policy intervention disbenefits (i.e., decreased speed, increased GHG, and increased fuel
953 consumption). While this SEM captured co-benefits including GHG reduction and climate
954 change mitigation, reduced travel time, reduced travel congestion, increased safety, etc., various
955 disbenefits were observed within the included studies. However, since disbenefits were beyond
956 the scope of the SEM, disbenefits were not officially documented. Finally, the Excel database
957 and the interactive visualization tool can be piloted amongst potential users and improved upon
958 accordingly.

959

960 We encourage practitioners and policy makers to use the resulting Excel database and the
961 interactive visualization tool to explore intervention options that can be implemented in their
962 urban areas, including options that they may have been previously unaware of. For example, an
963 intervention may be documented in Asia that has not been considered in Europe or the US or
964 vice-versa. Users can also dig deeper into the impact of these policy interventions on primary
965 outcomes (traffic emissions/TRAP), secondary outcomes (human exposures and health impacts),
966 and items of interest (for example, what co-benefits might be expected when a particular policy
967 intervention is implemented? What enablers and barriers may impact transferability potential?).

968 On the other hand, we encourage researchers to use the SEM resulting Excel database to explore
969 the current state of the evidence and formulate future (and more specific) research questions,
970 understand trends (for example, a researcher can use the SEM to understand which
971 interventions/outcomes have been studied most frequently and decide if there is enough evidence
972 available to conduct a systematic review on a particular intervention), and gaps in the literature
973 (for example, a researcher can identify if data is lacking for a certain intervention/outcome). Of
974 importance, only 3% of the included articles report on all elements of the full-chain (traffic
975 emissions, TRAP, human exposures, and health impacts) which is a gap to fill in and of itself.
976

977 **CONCLUSION**

978 This SEM represents the results of a challenging exercise to systematize our understanding of
979 which urban transport policies impact traffic emissions, TRAP, exposures, and human health.
980 Our findings provide valuable insight into the literature on urban policies to reduce traffic
981 emissions and TRAP. A total of 1,092 policy scenarios across 365 identified articles were
982 included in the SEM and an open-access Excel database. 58 unique policies were considered and
983 encompass pricing, land-use, infrastructure, behavioral, technology, and management, standards,
984 and services categories. A general finding was that while there are several policies implemented
985 or studied in urban areas that are expected to reduce emissions, and in turn reduce TRAP and
986 improve health outcomes, the associated evidence varies. We find that the body of evidence in
987 the literature reduces as we go down the full-chain between emissions, TRAP, exposures, and
988 health impacts. As noted previously, this is a likely function of how the transport sector is mostly
989 regulated based on traffic emissions, and that both pre-implementation and post-implementation
990 studies of effectiveness, and follow-up for health outcomes, are very rare. Several of the findings
991 similarly reinforce where gaps remain - often the types of strategies that are more
992 interdisciplinary in nature (such as behavioral and land use strategies) are neglected in favor of
993 supply-side measures usually implemented by transport authorities. We also noted gaps in
994 regional coverage of studies, indicating potential mismatch between where investigation is most
995 needed (i.e., rapidly urbanizing middle- and low-income nations), and where the studies are
996 currently focused on.

997 This work is, to our knowledge, the first of its kind to establish the scope of literature around
998 transport emissions, and TRAP reduction policies and to help answer the question of which ones
999 are shown to meaningfully reduce emissions, improve air quality, and reduce exposures and
1000 health impacts. While the volume of studies in this field limited the recency of studies included,
1001 and excluded gray literature, the findings, coupled with the user-friendly dissemination tools will
1002 remain a valuable resource for both academics and practitioners in this area.

1003 **AMENDMENTS**

1004 This SEM follows a previously published protocol (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.105826). All
1005 specific amendments, including the date of each amendment and a description of the change to
1006 this SEM, were documented, and are reported in the Supplementary Material (Table S.7).

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1017 For the purpose of Open Access, the author has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC
1018 BY) license to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising.

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1022 importing full-text articles into Covidence for full-text screening, Harry Williams for assisting
1023 HK with an ad-hoc review of data extraction, and Paul Whaley and Taylor Wolffe for their
1024 constructive and thoughtful comments during the conception of this work.

1025 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

1026 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

1027 **CONTRIBUTIONS**

1028 HK is the guarantor and conceived the idea of this SEM. HK and KS designed and drafted this
1029 SEM paper. MF conducted the literature searches. KS, HK, and JB screened studies against
1030 eligibility criteria. KS completed data extraction and coding for the Excel database. HK, TR, and
1031 JB reviewed data coding. HK and KS analyzed the extracted data. RJ created the interactive data
1032 visualization tool. All authors read, provided feedback, and approved the final manuscript.

1033

1034

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table S.1 Literature Search Details

Database	Line #	Search	Raw Hit Count
Public Affairs Index (Ebsco)	1	AB (exhaust n1 gas*) or TI (exhaust n1 gas*) or TI (emission* or pollut* or black carbon or elemental carbon or hydrocarbon* or carbon monoxide or (nitrogen n1 (oxide* or dioxide)) or nitric oxide or sulfur dioxide or particle* or particulate matter or PM2.5 or PM10 or PMcoarse or PMabsorbance or ultra fine particle* or UFP* or volatile organic compound* or VOCs) OR AB (emission* or pollut* or (black n2 carbon) or elemental carbon or hydrocarbon* or carbon monoxide or (nitrogen n1 (oxide* or dioxide)) or nitric oxide or sulfur dioxide or particle* or particulate matter or PM2.5 or PM10 or PMcoarse or PMabsorbance or ultra fine particle* or UFP* or volatile organic compound* or VOCs) OR DE "AIR pollutants" or DE "AIR pollution"	19,520
	2	TI ((automobile* or traffic* or car or cars or truck* or vehicle* or transport*)) OR AB ((automobile* or traffic* or car or cars or truck* or vehicle* or transport*))	29,255
	3	TI ((polic* or strateg* or practice* or management or regulation* or intervention*)) OR AB (polic* or or strateg* or practice* or management or regulation* or intervention*)) OR DE "GOVERNMENT policy"	189,196
		1 and 2 and 3 (limited to English and 2000-current)	907
TRID (only shows first 15000 hits)	1	(automobile* or traffic* or car or cars or truck* or vehicle* or transport*)	15000
	2	(urban or city or cities or metropolitan)	15000
	3	(pollution* or exhaust* or emission*)	15000
	4	(polic* or strateg* or practice* or management or regulation* or intervention*)	15000
		1 and 2 and 3 and 4 (limited to English, 2000-current, articles/papers)	4405
Medline Complete (Ebsco)	1	TI (emission* or pollut* or black carbon or elemental carbon or hydrocarbon* or carbon monoxide or (nitrogen n1 (oxide* or dioxide)) or nitric oxide or sulfur dioxide or particle* or particulate matter or PM2.5 or PM10 or PMcoarse or PMabsorbance or ultra fine particle* or UFP* or volatile organic compound* or VOCs) OR AB (emission* or pollut* or black carbon or elemental carbon or hydrocarbon* or carbon monoxide or (nitrogen n1 (oxide* or dioxide)) or nitric oxide or sulfur dioxide or particle* or particulate matter or PM2.5 or PM10 or PMcoarse or PMabsorbance or ultra fine	931,242

		particle* or UFP* or volatile organic compound* or OCs) OR (MH "Air Pollutants") OR (MH "Air Pollution+") OR (MH "Traffic-Related Pollution") OR (MH "Vehicle Emissions")	
	2	(MH "Automobiles") OR (MH "Automobile Driving")) OR (TI ((automobile* or traffic* or car or cars or truck* or vehicle* or transport*)) OR AB ((automobile* or traffic* or car or cars or truck* or vehicle* or transport*)))	755,074
	3	((MH "Public Policy+") OR (MH "Local Government") OR (MH "Policy Making+") OR (MH "Policy+")) OR (TI ((polic* or strateg* or practice* or management or regulation* or intervention*)) OR AB (polic* or strateg* or practice* or management or regulation* or intervention*)))	4,358,095
	4	((MH "Urban Population") OR (MH "Urban Health")) OR AB (urban or city or cities or metropolitan) OR TI (urban or city or cities or metropolitan)	313,442
		1 and 2 and 3 and 4 (limited to English and 2000-current)	1536
Embase (Ovid)	1	exp air pollution/	144368
	2	(nitrogen adj1 (oxide* or dioxide)).ti,ab.	10915
	3	"PM2.5".ti,ab.	15375
	4	(emission* or pollut* or hydrocarbon* or particle* or PM10 or PMcoarse or PMabsorbance or UFP* or volatile organic compound* or VOCs).ti,ab.	792284
	5	((black or elemental) adj1 carbon*).ti,ab.	7848
	6	((particulate adj2 matter) or (carbon adj1 monoxide) or (nitric adj1 oxide) or (sulfur adj1 dioxide)).ti,ab.	235053
	7	(volatile organic compound* or ultra fine particle*).ti,ab.	13195
	8	((exhaust adj1 gas*) or (gas* adj1 exhaust)).ti,ab.	1746
	9	exp exhaust gas/	18023
	10	or/1-9	1065034
	11	(automobile* or traffic* or car or cars or truck* or vehicle* or transport*).ti,ab.	877235
	12	exp car/	9019
	13	or/11-12	878615
	14	10 and 13	85733
	15	exp government regulation/ or exp health care policy/ or exp policy/	302360
	16	(polic* or strateg* or practice* or management or regulation* or intervention*).ti,ab.	5554987
	17	or/15-16	5702411

	18	exp urban health/ or exp urban area/ or exp urban population/	110872
	19	(urban or city or cities or metropolitan).ti,ab.	367072
	20	or/18-19	394110
	21	14 and 17 and 20	2569
	22	limit 21 to (english language and yr="2000 -Current")	2282

Table S.2 Reason for Article Exclusion at Full-Text Level

Attached to this submission as an Excel file.

Table S.3 Articles Screened in Duplicate at Title and Abstract Level

Attached to this submission as an Excel file.

Table S.4 Articles Screened in Duplicate at Full-Text Level

Attached to this submission as an Excel file.

Table S.5 Data Extraction and Coding

Data Category	Data Collected											
General Article Information <i>Data captured at study-level</i> <i>Required field</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reference ID ● Title ● Author(s) ● Publication Year ● Journal ● URL to full-text or abstract <p>All general article information will be collected as text entry.</p>											
Study Type <i>Data captured at study-level</i> <i>Required field</i>	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 80%;">Study Type</th> <th style="width: 20%;">Code</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> Case-Control <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in an observational study where two existing groups differing in outcome are identified and compared (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i> </td> <td style="text-align: center;">CC</td> </tr> <tr> <td> Case Report <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in a descriptive study of a single individual or three or fewer individuals (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i> </td> <td style="text-align: center;">CR</td> </tr> <tr> <td> Case Series/Case Study <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in a descriptive study of a group (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i> </td> <td style="text-align: center;">CS</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cohort</td> <td style="text-align: center;">CH</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Study Type	Code	Case-Control <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in an observational study where two existing groups differing in outcome are identified and compared (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i>	CC	Case Report <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in a descriptive study of a single individual or three or fewer individuals (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i>	CR	Case Series/Case Study <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in a descriptive study of a group (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i>	CS	Cohort	CH
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	<p><i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in a prospective study where a group of subjects (with a causative factor and free of a condition of interest) is followed up and observed for the occurrence of the condition (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i></p>																			
	<p>Cross Sectional <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure for participants by measuring the outcome and exposure at the same time (Setia, 2016).</i></p>	CE																		
	<p>Ecological Study <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure for different groups, rather than individuals. No individual level information is collected (e.g. zip codes used for comparison) (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i></p>	ES																		
	<p>Quasi-Experiment <i>Explores connection between outcome and exposure in an empirical interventional study that estimates the impact of an intervention on a target population without random assignment (e.g. participant allocation is done according to date of birth (odd or even) or hospital record number, etc.) (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i></p>	QE																		
	<p>Randomized Controlled Trial <i>Involves random assignments to either receive an intervention or a control for exploring the connection between outcome and exposure (Parab and Bhalerao, 2010).</i></p>	RT																		
	<p>If a study design other than those already listed occurs, it will be assigned a unique code, and it will be added to the category list for future use.</p>																			
<p>Urban Policy Intervention <i>Data captured at study-level</i> <i>Required field</i></p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="670 1560 1295 1598">Urban Policy Intervention</th> <th data-bbox="1295 1560 1528 1598">Code</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="2" data-bbox="670 1598 1528 1638" style="text-align: center;">Pricing</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1638 1295 1675">Air pollution charging fee</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1638 1528 1675">APC</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1675 1295 1713">Congestion charging</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1675 1528 1713">COC</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1713 1295 1751">Fuel taxes or price increase</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1713 1528 1751">FUT</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1751 1295 1789">Mileage-based user fees</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1751 1528 1789">MUF</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1789 1295 1827">Parking charges</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1789 1528 1827">PAC</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1827 1295 1864">Road pricing</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1827 1528 1864">ROP</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="670 1864 1295 1902">Pricing incentives</td> <td data-bbox="1295 1864 1528 1902">PRI</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Urban Policy Intervention	Code	Pricing		Air pollution charging fee	APC	Congestion charging	COC	Fuel taxes or price increase	FUT	Mileage-based user fees	MUF	Parking charges	PAC	Road pricing	ROP	Pricing incentives	PRI
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Vehicle ownership taxes	VOT
Land-use	
Development density and mixed developments	DMD
Parking expansion	PAE
Superblock development	SBD
Transit-oriented development	TOD
Urban sprawl	USP
Urban transport planning	UTP
Infrastructure	
Active transportation infrastructure	ATI
Bus rapid transit or mass rapid transit	BRT
Greenspace or blue space	GBS
Park and ride	PAR
Public transportation infrastructure	PTI
Roadway development	RDV
Solid roadside barrier	SRB
Speed bump development	SPB
Street ventilation	SVA
Unconventional intersection or intersection alteration	UCI
Vegetative roadside barrier, surface, or roof	VRB
Behavioral	
Active or non-motorized transport (i.e., bike or walk) promotion or shift	ATP
Flexible work arrangements	FWA
Public transit promotion or shift	PTP
Ride sharing promotion or shift	RSP
Technology	
Alternative fuel technology	AFT
Alternative vehicle technology	AVT
Electronic toll technology	ETT
Material coating	MCT
Real-time passenger information	RPI
Speed control technology	SCT
Stop/Start technology	SST
Vehicle retrofitting	VRF
Management, Standards and Services	
Fleet management	FLM
Fuel regulation or restriction	FRR
High occupancy vehicle lane	HOV
Inspection and maintenance program	IMP
Intelligent transport system	ITS
Low emission zone	LEZ
Loading, unloading, and/or idling regulation	LIR

	Parking standards, reduction or regulation	PAS
	Public transportation expansion	PTE
	Public transportation regulation	PTR
	Speed limit regulation or reduction	SRE
	Street cleaning	SCL
	Studded tire regulation	TRE
	Traffic signal optimization	TSO
	Vehicle or manufacturing alteration	VMA
	Vehicle emission regulation	VER
	Vehicle purchase restriction	VPR
	Vehicle rerouting or route optimization	VRR
	Vehicle retirement or replacement	VRP
	Vehicle shift	VES
	Vehicle use restriction	VUR
<p>If an urban policy intervention other than those already listed occurs, it will be assigned a unique code, and it will be added to the category list for future use. The urban policy interventions listed here were collected from KonSULT (University of Leeds, 2016), expert knowledge and other relevant reviews.</p>		
Data for the categories above will be collected at the study-level.		
Data for the categories below will be collected at the intervention-level.		
Policy Packaging <i>Data captured at intervention-level</i> <i>Required field</i>	Is the intervention part of a policy package?	Code
	Yes	Y
	No	N
Method(s) Used <i>Data captured at intervention-level</i> <i>Required field</i>	Method(s) Used	Code
	Measurement	ME
	Modeling	MO
	Both Methods	B
	Method(s) used refers to whether measurement, modeling or both methods were utilized in the study.	
Population Characteristics <i>Data captured at intervention-level</i> <i>Required field</i>	Age	Code
	Infant (< 2 years old)	INF
	Child (2-12 years old)	CHI
	Adolescent (13-17 years old)	ADO
	Adult (18-65 years old)	ADT
	Elderly (> 65 years old)	ELD
	All ages	ALL
	Gender	Code
	Both genders	BG

	Female	F																																																				
	Male	M																																																				
	Race/Ethnicity	Code																																																				
	African	AF																																																				
	Asian	AS																																																				
	Hispanic/Latino	HL																																																				
	Middle Eastern	ME																																																				
	Native American	NA																																																				
	Pacific Islander	PI																																																				
	White/Caucasian	WH																																																				
	Multiple (more than one)	MU																																																				
	All races/ethnicities	ALL																																																				
	<p>All applicable population characteristics across age, gender, and race/ethnicity will be selected.</p> <p>If a population characteristic for age, gender, or race/ethnicity other than those already listed occurs, it will be assigned a unique code, and it will be added to the appropriate category list for future use.</p>																																																					
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	Nitric oxide	NO
	Nitrogen dioxide	NO2
	Nitrogen oxides	NOX
	Organic carbon	OC
	Particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 1 micrometer	PM1
	Particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 2.5 micrometers	PM2.5
	Particulate matter with a diameter equal to or less than 10 micrometers	PM10
	PM _{absorbance}	PMA
	Particulate matter with diameters of mixed or unspecified sizes	PMX
	Reactive organic gases	ROG
	Respirable suspended particulate matter	RSPM
	Secondary organic aerosols	SOA
	Sulfur dioxide	SO2
	Sulfure oxides	SOX
	Suspended particulate matter	SPM
	Total carbon	TC
	Total organic gases	TOG
	Ultrafine particles	UFP
	Volatile organic compounds	VOC
	Other	OTH

All applicable pollutants will be selected. If a pollutant other than those already listed occurs, it will be assigned a unique code, and it will be added to the category list for future use.

Traffic Emission Effects
Data captured at intervention-level
Required field

Is effect on traffic emissions reported?	Code
Yes	Y
No	N

What is the direction of the effect on traffic emissions?	Code
Reduction	ER
Increase	EI
Mixed effect	EM
No change	EN

Traffic-Related Air Pollution (TRAP) Effects
Data captured at intervention-level
Required field

Is effect on TRAP reported?	Code
Yes	Y
No	N

	<table border="1"> <tr> <th data-bbox="683 191 1292 226">What is the direction of the effect on TRAP?</th> <th data-bbox="1292 191 1528 226">Code</th> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 226 1292 262">Reduction</td> <td data-bbox="1292 226 1528 262">TR</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 262 1292 298">Increase</td> <td data-bbox="1292 262 1528 298">TI</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 298 1292 333">Mixed effect</td> <td data-bbox="1292 298 1528 333">TM</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 333 1292 369">No change</td> <td data-bbox="1292 333 1528 369">TN</td> </tr> </table> <p data-bbox="667 422 1463 457">The effect on TRAP is measured as air quality concentrations.</p>	What is the direction of the effect on TRAP?	Code	Reduction	TR	Increase	TI	Mixed effect	TM	No change	TN																		
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<p data-bbox="203 1474 418 1509">Health Impacts</p> <p data-bbox="203 1509 597 1579"><i>Data captured at intervention-level</i></p> <p data-bbox="203 1579 386 1614"><i>Optional field</i></p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <th data-bbox="683 1505 1292 1614">Are health impacts reported? (The study went a step further to investigate health impacts related to TRAP)</th> <th data-bbox="1292 1505 1528 1614">Code</th> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 1614 1292 1650">Yes</td> <td data-bbox="1292 1614 1528 1650">Y</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 1650 1292 1686">No</td> <td data-bbox="1292 1650 1528 1686">N</td> </tr> </table> <p data-bbox="667 1732 1339 1768">If yes, health impacts will be categorized as follows:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <th data-bbox="683 1768 1292 1803">Health Impact Category</th> <th data-bbox="1292 1768 1528 1803">Code</th> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 1803 1292 1839">Activity effects</td> <td data-bbox="1292 1803 1528 1839">AE</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="683 1839 1292 1875">Allergy effects</td> <td data-bbox="1292 1839 1528 1875">AL</td> </tr> </table>	Are health impacts reported? (The study went a step further to investigate health impacts related to TRAP)	Code	Yes	Y	No	N	Health Impact Category	Code	Activity effects	AE	Allergy effects	AL																
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	Cerebrovascular effects	CE																				
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	Hospitalization	HP																				
	Metabolic outcomes	MO																				
	Neurological or cognitive disorders	NC																				
	Premature mortality	PM																				
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Table S.6 Studies with Missing Data

Attached to this submission as an Excel file.

Table S.7 Amendments

Date of amendment	Description of change	Reason for amendment
June 1, 2020	We used Covidence software (Veritas Health Innovation, n.d.) instead of Rayyan QCRI (Ouzzani et al., 2016) for the screening process. The use of Covidence also eliminated the need to use Mendeley for removing duplicates.	This amendment was adopted because Covidence software streamlined the screening process. For example, Covidence automatically identified and removed duplicates, whereas Rayyan QCRI would have required an extra step to remove duplicates (in Mendeley) before screening. Additionally, we did not have to create two separate folders for screening articles at each level (title and abstract level and full-text level) as we would have needed with Rayyan QCRI. Covidence can store studies for each screening level in one folder.
June 24, 2020	We added an exclusion criterion for additional clarification: “Articles that are not original studies or do not provide original data (e.g., reviews)”	This amendment was adopted because this was the authors’ original intention, and the authors later realized that this exclusion criterion was not explicitly stated in the protocol. We added the exclusion criterion in the eligibility criteria of the final SEM to clarify the exact criteria used for the screening process.
June 24, 2020	We added an exclusion criterion: “Articles that are conference or symposium proceedings”.	This amendment was adopted because this was the authors’ original intention for the exclusion reason “Articles that are not peer-reviewed” because conference and symposium proceedings are not typically peer-reviewed articles. The authors later realized that this did not explicitly explain that conference or symposium proceedings would be excluded per the original exclusion reason. We added this exclusion reason in the eligibility criteria of the final SEM to clarify the exact criteria used for the screening process.
July 22, 2020	We eliminated “specifically” from inclusion criteria when referring to “Articles which	This amendment was adopted to eliminate ambiguity. We consider interventions that specifically aim to reduce traffic emissions/TRAP as well as those that

	specifically investigate urban-level policy interventions’ impact on traffic emissions (exhaust or non-exhaust) and/or TRAP originating from mobile on-road traffic: BC, elemental carbon (EC), hydrocarbons (HCs), carbon monoxide (CO), nitric oxide (NO), NO ₂ , NO _x , sulfur dioxide (SO ₂), PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , difference between PM ₁₀ and PM _{2.5} (PM _{coarse}), blackness of PM filters as a representation of BC or EC (PM _{absorbance}), particulate matter with diameters of mixed sizes (PM _x), UFP, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) or other traffic-related air pollutants/pollution”.	did not specifically aim to reduce traffic emissions/TRAP but still observed this effect. For example, an intervention reducing speed limits to reduce crashes also saw an effect on traffic emissions, and this was included.
August 4, 2020	We added an inclusion criterion: “Articles which investigate past, current, future (hypothetical) or hypothetical changes in traffic emissions and/or TRAP”.	This amendment was adopted to clarify that we will include studies that may model the future impact of an intervention on traffic emission/TRAP changes in addition to past and current changes and the impacts of hypothetical/counterfactual scenarios.
November 2, 2020	We updated the code for the policy intervention “Vehicle Retrofitting” from “VER” to “VRF”.	This amendment was adopted because VER code was already used for the policy intervention “Vehicle Emissions Regulation”. This does not indicate that these policies were merged into one group, rather, these two policies initially used the same code (VER) so one needed to be changed to ensure no duplicate codes were used.
November 11, 2020	We added a category “Policy Packaging” for data extraction.	This amendment was adopted to capture more detail on whether the recorded policy intervention is part of a policy package (i.e., 2 or more policies implemented in the same place at the same time) or not (i.e., only 1 policy implemented).
November 11, 2020	We added an enabler and barrier category “Land-use” for data extraction	This amendment was adopted to capture more detail on potential enablers and barriers to urban policy implementation regarding land-use.
November 11, 2020	We eliminated a category “Population Baseline Conditions” for data extraction.	This amendment was adopted because no studies reported on this category, and it was not feasible to contact authors for all studies for this information.

		Additionally, this information does not affect the scope or focus of the SEM and SEM database as the primary focus on urban policy interventions and their effects on traffic emission/TRAP is still addressed.
November 11, 2020	We added an exclusion criterion: “Articles that investigate a policy proxy (e.g. strikes, lockdowns, etc.)	This amendment was adopted to eliminate ambiguity. Policy proxies, rather than explicit policy interventions, are not part of the intended scope of this SEM.
November 25, 2020	We added two categories to “Population Ethnicity” 1) Middle Eastern and 2) Multiple (more than one), and we updated “African-American” to “African”	This amendment was adopted to further detail documented population ethnicities. Middle Eastern populations may be more directly classified. Further, we will use “Multiple (more than one)” category for populations that tend to be more diverse in nature. Specifically, if a city does not have a single majority ethnicity that composes >60% of the total city population, then it will be categorized as “Multiple (more than one)”. Additionally, “African” category shall refer to studies focused on populations in Africa. We altered this category from “African-American” since US populations will be classified as “Multiple (more than one)” as they do not have a single ethnicity that composes >60% of the total city populations considered.
December 1, 2020	We added two exclusion criteria: 1) “Articles that do not investigate a policy intervention (e.g. source apportionment studies)” and 2) “Articles that are books, books chapters, or reports”	This amendment was adopted to 1) clarify our focus on the effects of policy interventions. Articles that did not investigate a policy intervention(s) (e.g. source apportionment studies) are not part of the intended scope of this SEM. And 2) to clarify that we treated these types of articles (books, book chapters or reports) as gray literature which is not included as it is beyond the scope of the SEM.
December 1, 2020	We updated an exclusion criterion: “Articles which exclusively investigate policy interventions implemented in rural areas” to “Articles which exclusively investigate policy interventions implemented in non-urban areas (e.g. rural areas)”	This amendment was adopted to clarify our focus on urban-level policy interventions. Suburban and rural areas will not be considered as they are beyond the intended scope of this SEM.
September 28, 2021	We combined similar categories for co-benefits, enablers, and barriers. Co-benefits:	This amendment was adopted to simplify the data extraction and coding process since some of the categories are similar (i.e., greenhouse gas emission reduction inherently implies climate change

	GG and CC → GG Barriers: BG, BL, and BP → BG Enablers: EG, EL, and EP → EG	mitigation). Furthermore, the authors aim to improve usability and understanding of the database for its users.
November 1, 2021	Three authors will review the coded data for consistency instead of two.	This amendment was adopted due to time and resource limitations of the available reviewers. All reviewers documented their notes of identified discrepancies and shared with KS to achieve a resolution.

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